

THE EFFECT OF MANAGEMENT CONTROL SYSTEM THROUGH THE LEVERS OF CONTROL FRAMEWORK ON PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN THE LOCAL RESTAURANT SECTOR

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of the Management Control System (MCS) on the performance of SMEs. The study was conducted on local restaurant SMEs managers in Tangerang, Indonesia. The number of respondents in this study was 129 local restaurant managers. This study uses the Levers of Control framework introduced by Simon (1995), namely beliefs systems, boundary systems, diagnostic control systems, and interactive control systems, as MCS variables. This study uses a structural equation model as an analytical tool and STATA software to process data using a questionnaire as a research instrument. The results showed that belief systems had no significant effect on performance SMEs, boundary systems had no significant effect on performance SMEs, diagnostic control systems had a significant effect on performance SMEs, and interactive control systems had a significant effect on performance SMEs. The implication of this research is that it can provide a choice of a control system for the management of SMEs which has so far used conventional control systems and illustrates that the control system for the management of SMEs in local restaurants can help achieve business goals as planned.

Keywords: Management Control System, Levers of Control, Performance SMEs

1. INTRODUCTION

A management control system (MCS) is a system that is very important for the organization. (Armes & Salarzahi, 2010) said that a management control system is a system that collects and uses information to evaluate the performance of different organizational resources such as human, physical, financial, and also the organization as a whole by considering the organization's strategy. MCS is a tool used by managers to achieve company goals by controlling available resources (Ismail, 2016). With the MCS, the organization can monitor the activities carried out by management. In addition, MCS aims to provide useful information for managerial decision-making, planning, monitoring, and evaluation of organizational activities by changing employee behaviour. (Merchant,

K., Van der Stede, 2016). The management control system is a broad concept and consists of many elements and is used for different purposes (Mahama, 2006). The management control system is also known as many elements that work together (Otley, 1999). (Simons, 1995) introduced an MCS element known as the levers of control (LoC). LoC consists of four types, namely belief system, boundary system, diagnostic control system, and interactive control system. A good MCS guarantees success for an organization. Companies that implement a management control system will achieve increased performance. The management control system must be designed to support the company's chosen strategy in order to gain a competitive advantage and superior company performance (Gani, 2012). Performance instability is usually caused by the ineffectiveness of the management control system implemented by the company. Company performance is the level of success in achieving company goals (Roth & Jackson, 1995). (Mahama, 2006)states that the performance measurement system has a positive effect on organizational performance. Performance measurement is part of the company's management control system. Therefore the company tries to reflect the company's orientation in the management control system (Langfield-Smith, 1997).

SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) is a form of the people's economy that are considered to have a strategic role and potential in driving the national economy (Ismail et al., 2019). In recent years, many SMEs engaged in trading, manufacturing, restaurants, and so on have faced changes in their business due to dynamic changes in the business environment. This happened because of the free market era which led to the entry of foreign businesses and also the development of several modern businesses such as supermarkets, mini-markets, industries, and so on. This condition causes SMEs to be at a very tight level of competition due to regulations that allow the development of modern businesses, even those from abroad. Often these regulations are not in line with government regulations that aim to protect SMEs, which are generally community businesses that have been running for a long period of time.

The development of SMEs in Indonesia faces various obstacles, including the lack of quality resources, product marketing, raw materials, and capital (Meutia, 2017). SMEs face major obstacles compared to modern businesses, especially from the business management system, such as limited capital, limited access to sources of capital, relatively low human resource education, lack of business networks, and so on. A business or business organization that is formed with a specific purpose must be able to utilize the resources it has in order to win business competition, maximize profits, answer challenges and take advantage of opportunities in running its business (Salman Jumaili, 2006). According to (Simons, 1995) MCS is a formal process, based on routine information and procedures used by managers to maintain or change organizational activity patterns. MCS includes management accounting systems, budget practices, performance measurement systems, project management systems, planning systems, and reporting systems.

Various studies have been conducted in the management accounting literature that examines the contribution of MCS in improving organizational performance (Davila & Venkatachalam, 2004), but research observing MCS on performance in SMEs is still limited. According to (Ismail et al., 2019) Indonesian public participation in the SME sector is still low. This is proven because only 24% of the population is involved in Indonesia. Therefore, a study is needed to examine the implementation of MCS and the performance of SMEs in Indonesia. Several previous studies have observed how MCS is used for SMEs (M Acquaah, 2016);(Ismail, 2016), even though about 90% of all businesses worldwide are in the SME sector(Moses Acquaah, 2013). One of the studies in developed countries, namely the Netherlands (Pešalj et al., 2018) said that MCS through the LoC concept is used simultaneously to manage performance, especially in SMEs by using various data sources and analytical methods, including interviews and participant observation. The study findings identify managerial practices that enable the interaction of the four LoC elements that help organizations manage their organizations in terms of short and long-term focus, predictable goal attainment, seeking new opportunities, internal and external focus, and control and creativity. The SMEs research aims to advance research on integrating various aspects of performance management, especially technical and social. Based on this research, performance managers require active and sustainable use of the four control systems.

Based on the above phenomenon and referring to previous research, this study will examine the effect of MCS on the performance of SMEs in developing countries through the levers of control (LoC) approach. The SMEs used in this study are in the local restaurant sector that meets the criteria. LoC consists of belief systems, boundary systems, diagnostic control systems, and interactive control systems. This research study uses the contingency theory approach. The contingency theory emerged as a very basic part because various studies were conducted to look for the nature of contingencies in accounting (Abernethy & Lillis, 1995). The contingency approach is growing fast in the field of management accounting.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contingency theory assesses organizational performance will depend heavily on the fit between organizational contextual factors (Cadez & Guilding, 2008). According to (Simons, 1995) MCS is seen as a formal procedure and system that uses information to achieve or change various patterns in organizational activity. Regarding this definition, Simons said that MCS includes planning systems, reporting systems, and monitoring procedures that are based on the use of information. MCS is a process to influence the organization. The purpose of the MCS is to provide information that is useful in decision-making, planning, control, and evaluation (Widener, 2007). Therefore, MCS is basically a system composed of complementary components. This means that the use of each MCS element must be used together in order to have strength in its implementation. The role of MCS is very large for a company or organization. In business sector companies, failure to implement the MCS will result in damage to the company's reputation, huge financial losses, and the end of the organization(Merchant, K., Van der Stede, 2016). Furthermore

(Simons, 1995) divides the types of formal control into several types which are achieved by integrating four levers. The four control systems are known as the levers of control. The four types of control are belief systems explaining the core values of the organization, boundary systems explaining to employees what they cannot do, diagnostic control systems motivating employees to do and aligning employee behaviour with organizational goals, and providing monitoring mechanisms, while interactive control system, namely the process of two-way communication between managers and subordinates at various levels of the organization.

Company performance is an indicator of the level of success in achieving company goals (Roth & Jackson, 1995). (Mahama, 2006)states that the performance measurement system has a positive effect on organizational performance. Performance measurement is part of the company's management control system. Therefore the company tries to reflect the company's orientation in the management control system (Langfield-smith, 1997). Firm performance can be measured through financial performance and non-financial performance(Chow & Van der Stede, 2006). The combination of performance measurements and the level of management control is based on previous findings where it is no longer relevant to use only performance measures (Marginson et al., 2014). There are performance measures financial and non-financial with different results(Hartmann et al., 2010). Previous findings indicate that financial performance measurement can affect the performance of employees and managers. The use of financial performance measurement has many weaknesses in concepts, measures, and methods and does not yet provide a good explanation of the relationship between superiors and subordinates(Afrizal et al., 2020). So far, the performance of managers and subordinates is determined based on financial and non-financial performance measures (Chong M. Lau, 2015). Financial size can be measured through Cost, Profitability, Sales, and Market Share (Moorman, 1999). Non-financial performance measures such as customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, product innovation, and others (Davila & Venkatachalam, 2004). Performance measurement translates desired behaviour and results, also communicates company expectations, monitors progress, provides feedback, and motivates employees through rewards and sanctions (Chow & Van der Stede, 2006)

Several empirical studies provide evidence that there is a link between performance measurement systems and organizational performance (Mahama, 2006).(Ratmono & Nahartyo, 2012)formulating the hypothesis that the relationship between MCS and performance is an indirect relationship because it has to go through innovation as a mediator, however the research findings show that MCS has a direct effect on performance. The research findings support the LoC theory that organizations that integrate the four control systems in a control package can improve organizational performance. This is confirmed by Jamil and Mohamed (2013) who state that there is a link between MCS and performance.(Jamil & Mohamed, 2013)examines the effect of MCS on performance measurement systems using LoC. The results showed that of the four LoCs used, namely the beliefs system, boundary system, diagnostic control system, and interactive control system, it turned out that only the diagnostic control system had a

positive and significant effect on performance. While the belief system, boundary system and interactive control system have a positive effect on performance but not significant. Lever of control in research conducted by (Afrizal et al., 2020) does not use a belief system and boundary system but This study uses only two control systems of levers of control are: diagnostic control system and interactive control system in the dimensional measurement of objective and subjective as that of (Marginson et al., 2014). (Henri, 2006) found that managers who use performance measures on control system diagnostics and interactive control systems can improve the organization. There is evidence of interdependence and complementarity between the four levers of control. The full benefits of performance measurement appear when using the diagnostics control system and interactive control system (Ferreira & Otley, 2009); (Hoque & Chia, 2012) (Tessier & Otley, 2012).

The study of Management control system as control is closely related to contingency theory. Contingency theory views that if an organization wants to have good performance, it must adapt its management control system design to conditions of uncertainty, for example from the environment, organizational size, and business strategy (Govindarajan & Fisher, 1990) (Chenhall, 2007). The contingency approach is carried out on the basis of contingency theory. The contingency approach refers to the condition that there is no single best organizational design, which is applied in an organization and the assumption that various organizational designs have the same probability of outcome or performance (Chenhall, 2007). The introduction of the contingency model from modern organizational theory has contributed to the development of management accounting, especially in explaining the factors that affect organizational performance.

Based on the description above, the research hypothesis is as follows:

- H1: MCS based on the belief system has a significant effect on the performance of SMEs.
- H2: MCS based on the boundary system has a significant effect on the performance of SMEs.
- H3: MCS based on an interactive control system has a significant effect on the performance of SMEs.
- H4: MCS based on a diagnostic control system has a significant effect on the performance of SMEs.

3. METHODOLOGY

Sampling Method:

The research sample was taken using a purposive sampling method for SME managers in Tangerang, Indonesia by giving questionnaires to SMEs leaders directly. Primary data was obtained using a research instrument in the form of a questionnaire. A total of 189 questionnaires were distributed to owners or leaders who run SMEs in the local restaurant sector, and 129 questionnaires were returned. The instrument was measured using a

Likert scale of 5 points, namely strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4) strongly agree (5) with the question items. In this study the sampling with the following criteria:

1. SMEs managers in Tangerang in the local restaurant business sector;
2. Have managed SMEs for at least 3 years.

Variable Measurement and Research Instruments:

According to (Sakaran, 2016) a variable is anything that can make a difference or bring variation to a value. Values can be different at different times for the same object or person or at the same time for different objects or people. Variables must be operationally defined so that it is easier to find the relationship between one variable and another and its measurement. In this study, it consists of 4 exogenous variables, namely belief systems, boundary systems, diagnostic control systems, and interactive control systems, and endogenous variables, namely company performance.

Independent Variables namely Management Control System (MCS),

MCS with the Simons Lever of Control approach consists of four dimensions, namely, beliefs system, boundary system, diagnostic control system, and interactive control system

1. Belief systems (BFS)

Beliefs system is a set of organizational definitions that are explicitly communicated by senior managers in a formal manner and systematically enforced to provide basic values, goals and direction for the organization (Simons, 1995). To measure the variable system beliefs used indicators developed by (Widener, 2007).

The indicators used in the BFS variable:

- a. The organization's mission can communicate the company's core values
- b. Leaders communicate organizational values
- c. Employee awareness of organizational values
- d. The organization's mission inspires employees to work

2. Boundary system (BOS)

Boundary system motivates employees to seek new ideas and new ideas. The indicators for measuring the boundary system refer to the concept (Simons, 1995) developed by (Widener, 2007). The indicators used in the BOS variable:

- a. Code of ethics that describes behaviour according to employees
- b. The code of ethics informs about behaviour that is out of bounds
- c. Communicating risks so they can be avoided
- d. Employees are aware of the company's code of ethics

3. Diagnostic Control System (DCS)

According to (Henri, 2006) a control system that can develop new ideas and initiatives and emerging directions from the ground up with a focus on strategic uncertainty.

Indicators used in the DCS variable:

- a. Review progress towards company goals
- b. Monitor the results achieved
- c. Compare the results achieved with the planned
- d. Review the key steps to success

4. Interactive Control Systems (ICS)

According to (Simon, 2006) an interactive control system aims to improve the ability of managers to anticipate effectively in managing future uncertainties. Interactive control systems are formal systems used by top managers to involve themselves regularly and personally in the decision-making activities of subordinates. This study uses indicators developed by (Widener, 2007).

Indicators used in the ICS variable:

- a. Develop discussions in meetings between superiors, subordinates and colleagues
- b. Develop challenges and debates based on data, assumptions and action plans
- c. Provides an organizational view
- d. Commitment to organization
- e. Focus on the main problem
- f. Focus on success factors
- g. Develop a common language in the organization

The Dependent Variable is the Performance of SMEs

Company performance is a measure of the company's success in achieving financial and non-financial goals (Bisbe & Otley, 2004). Company performance can be measured through two aspects, namely financial and non-financial performance (Chow & Van der Stede, 2006). The instrument used in this research is the developed instrument (Moorman, 1999). The company's performance has three indicators, namely financial performance, customer relationship performance and new product performance.

The indicators used in the Firm Performance variable:

a. Financial Performance:

Cost: The Company incurs costs according to the target

Sales: The Company is able to achieve the targeted sales growth

Profitability: The Company is able to achieve the targeted profits

Market share: The Company is able to control the market share that has been targeted

b. Customer Relationship Performance:

Customer satisfaction: My Company satisfies customers

Customer retention: My Company has loyal customers who buy product return

c. New product performance:

Speed of new product development: My Company is fast in developing products

Creativity of new product development: My Company develops products that innovative

Data analysis technique:

Testing of each of the proposed hypotheses can be done with multiple linear regression. Multiple linear regression testing using STATA statistical software. In this study, the multiple regression model to be developed is as follows:

$$\text{SMEs Performance} = a + b_1\text{Beliefs system} + b_2\text{Boundary system} + b_3\text{Diagnostic control system} + b_4\text{Interactive control system} + e$$

4. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In table 1 there are details of returning questionnaires sent as many as 189 questionnaires. There were 129 questionnaires that returned, so that 68% of the questionnaires that could be processed were processed. The details for sending and returning the questionnaire are in the following table. :

Table 1: Questionnaire Return Details

Information	Amount	Percentage
Sent questionnaires	189	100%
Unreturned questionnaires	60	32%
Questionnaires that can be processed	129	68%

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Table 2 shows that n for each valid variable is 129. Belief systems, boundary systems, diagnostic control systems, and interactive control systems, and performance have a standard deviation value that is smaller than the average value, this shows the distribution of data variables that are small

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
BFS	129	17.54264	1.111079	14	20
BOS	129	17.17054	1.606257	13	20
DCS	129	18.13953	.7780603	16	20
ICS	129	32.12403	1.340521	28	35
FP	129	36.17829	1.47611	32	40

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Table 3: Validity test

Item	Obs	Sign	item-test correlation	item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	alpha
BFS1	129	+	0.3997	0.3123	.0279429	0.7504
BFS2	129	+	0.1799	0.0368	.0299773	0.7735
BFS3	129	-	0.1489	0.0005	.0304046	0.7774
D	129	-	0.4813	0.4077	.0274812	0.7456
BOS1	129	-	0.2327	0.1198	.0292843	0.7629
BOS2	129	-	0.1115	-0.0301	.0307623	0.7781
BOS3	129	-	0.5358	0.4154	.0255922	0.7426
BOS4	129	-	0.6551	0.5975	.026097	0.7349
DCS1	129	+	0.4960	0.4236	.0273733	0.7448
DCS2	129	+	0.4312	0.3631	.0280821	0.7487
DCS3	129	+	0.0757	-0.0075	.0304619	0.7659
DCS4	129	-	0.5772	0.5069	.0265359	0.7392
ICS1	129	+	0.5363	0.4616	.0268608	0.7419
ICS2	129	+	0.5180	0.4588	.0276064	0.7447
ICS3	129	-	0.0591	-0.0199	.0305408	0.7659
ICS4	129	-	0.6066	0.5414	.0263782	0.7376
ICS5	129	+	0.5236	0.4493	.02702	0.7428
ICS6	129	+	0.4333	0.3530	.0277737	0.7483
ICS7	129	+	0.0909	0.0121	.0303317	0.7645
FP1	129	+	0.5171	0.4398	.0269948	0.7430
FP2	129	+	0.4531	0.3831	.0278459	0.7475
FP3	129	+	0.0841	-0.0043	.0304418	0.7665
FP4	129	-	0.6574	0.6036	.0262843	0.7357
FP5	129	+	0.5249	0.4551	.0271569	0.7431
FP6	129	+	0.4112	0.3339	.0280369	0.7496
FP7	129	-	0.0258	-0.0312	.0305583	0.7637
FP8	129	-	0.6246	0.5654	.0264375	0.7372
Test scale					.0281579	0.7592

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Table 4: Normalitas Test

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Table 5: Multiple Linear Regression Test

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	129
Model	179.966203	4	44.9915507	F(4, 124)	=	56.39
Residual	98.9330219	124	.797846951	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	278.899225	128	2.17890019	R-squared	=	0.6453
				Adj R-squared	=	0.6338
				Root MSE	=	.89322

FP	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
BOS	.0064176	.0522111	0.12	0.902	-.0969229 .109758
BFS	.1170963	.0754544	1.55	0.123	-.032249 .2664417
DCS	.8135909	.1339561	6.07	0.000	.5484542 1.078727
ICS	.4812622	.0770755	6.24	0.000	.3287082 .6338163
_cons	3.795681	2.371933	1.60	0.112	-.8990392 8.490401

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the table above, exogenous variables have a partially significant effect on endogenous because they have a significance value of less than 0.05 wherein column t is the value of the partial t test. It is said to be significant at the 5% level if the column on the right is P> [t] or it is also called value/significance <0.05 then based on the results of hypothesis testing shows that:

MCS based on the belief system (BFS) has a positive effect of 0.117 and not significant at 0.123 (1.55 > 1.34) on the performance of SMEs, MCS based on the boundary system

(BOS) has a positive effect of 0.064 and not significant at 0.902 ($0.12 < 1.34$) on the performance of SMEs, MCS based on the diagnostic control system(DCS) has a positive effect of 0.814 and a significant value of 0.000 ($6.07 > 1.34$) on the performance of SMEs, MCS based on the interactive control system (ICS)has a positive effect of 0.481 and a significant value of 0.000 ($6.24 > 1.34$) on the performance of SMEs.

For the F table is 1.34 meanwhile the standard error of estimate of the regression model is good to be used as a forecasting model because Root MSE < Standard deviation of the dependent variable.

Based on table 5 above, for the hypothesis 1, system beliefs have no effect on the performance of SMEs in the local restaurant sector in Tangerang, Indonesia. The results of hypothesis testing show that the significance level is 0.123, then it is above 0.05. This finding shows that the hypothesis 1 is not supported. The results of this study are in line with the findings of a study conducted by (Handayani & Bastian, 2017) that of the four levers of control (LOC) applied by an organizational belief system, there is no significant effect. However, when viewed from the correlation, the belief system on the performance of SMEs has a positive correlation. The belief system has no effect on performance because employees or employees of local restaurants do not fully understand the organization's vision and mission and main values of the organization. Employees do not understand the vision, mission, and main values of the organization because the leaders or owners have not fully socialized the importance of the vision, mission, and main values of the organization seriously. Leaders may only communicate to employees about the main values of the organization and the vision and mission of the organization, but employees do not respond positively. Thus, the leadership of the organization really needs to socialize and implement the vision, mission, and values properly, with the hope that employees are aware of the importance of the vision, mission, and main values of the organization which ultimately have an impact on improving organizational performance. Mission and core values of the organization seriously. Leaders may only communicate to employees about the main values of the organization and the vision and mission of the organization, but employees do not respond positively. Thus, the leadership of the organization really needs to socialize and implement the vision, mission, and values properly, with the hope that employees are aware of the importance of the vision, mission, and main values of the organization which ultimately have an impact on improving organizational performance. Mission and core values of the organization seriously. Leaders may only communicate to employees about the main values of the organization and the vision and mission of the organization, but employees do not respond positively. Thus, the leadership of the organization really needs to socialize and implement the vision, mission, and values properly, with the hope that employees are aware of the importance of the vision, mission, and main values of the organization which ultimately have an impact on improving organizational performance.

For hypothesis 2, the boundary system has no effect on the performance of SMEs in the local restaurant sector in Tangerang, Indonesia. The results of hypothesis testing show that the significance level is 0.902, then it is above 0.05. This finding shows that the

hypothesis 2 is not supported. The results of this study are in line with the findings of a study conducted by (Jamil & Mohamed, 2013) ; (Sutoyo & Mahardhika, 2015) that the four levers of control (LOC) applied by a boundary system organization have no a significant effect. However, when viewed from the correlation, the boundary system on the performance of SMEs has a positive correlation.

For the hypothesis 3, the diagnostic control system affects the performance of SMEs in the local restaurant sector in Tangerang, Indonesia. The results of hypothesis testing show that the significance level is 0.000, then it is below 0.05. This finding shows that the hypothesis 3 is supported. The results of this study are in line with the findings of a study conducted by (Jamil & Mohamed, 2013); (Afrizal et al., 2020) that the four levers of control (LOC) applied by a diagnostic control system organization have a significant effect. And when viewed from the correlation, the diagnostic control system on the performance of SMEs has a positive correlation. A diagnostic control system has a significant influence on performance. This can happen because the more an organization implements a diagnostic control system, the more significantly the organization's performance will improve. Diagnostic control systems such as accounting information systems have an important role in communicating practices and strategies to stakeholders. Therefore, by actively implementing a diagnostic control system, stakeholders know that management has monitored organizational performance (Jamil and Mohamed, 2013)

For the hypothesis 4, the interactive control system influences the performance of SMEs in the local restaurant sector in Tangerang, Indonesia. The results of hypothesis testing show that the significance level is 0.000, then it is below 0.05. This finding shows that the hypothesis 4 is supported. The results of this study are in line with the findings of research conducted by (Handayani & Bastian, 2017) ; (Afrizal et al., 2020). And when viewed from the correlation, the interactive control system on the performance of SMEs has a positive correlation. An interactive control system has a significant influence on performance. This can happen because the more an organization implements an interactive control system, the more significantly the performance of the organization will increase. Organizational leaders dialogue interactively with subordinates or employees. This is in accordance with the statement (Simons, 1995) interactive control system is a formal system used by top managers (leaders) to involve themselves regularly and personally in the decision-making activities of subordinates. Thus, it is very important for leaders to interact with subordinates or employees to implement a management control system in order to improve organizational performance.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded from this study that MCS based on beliefs systems and boundary systems has no significant effect on the performance of SMEs in the local restaurant sector in Tangerang, Indonesia. Meanwhile, based on the MCS diagnostic control systems, interactive control systems have a significant effect on the performance of SMEs in local restaurants in Tangerang, Indonesia. The limitation of the research is that there are questionnaires that are not

returned and filled in by respondents so that the data is not optimal. The suggestions for further research are expected to add moderating or intervening variables as well as a wider scope of objects so as to increase the effectiveness of levers of control on organizational performance both from various sectors.

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